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**Spatial Modelling Methods for
Forest Site Classification in Mountain Areas:
Development, Implementation, and Evaluation**

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Preface

This article is, to a largely extent, the collective synthesis of my cumulative dissertation thesis for obtaining a doctoral degree from the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna. The thesis was supervised by Ao. Univ.Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Klaus Katzensteiner and the two advisors, Univ.Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr. Georg Gratzer from the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna and Assoz. Univ.Prof. Dr. Clemens Geitner from the University of Innsbruck. I would like to express my gratitude to these persons and all other people who made this work possible. In 2022, I received the KUBIENA research award of the Austrian Soil Science Association for my dissertation.

The topic is on spatial modelling methods for forest site classification in mountain areas and builds on four scientific publications which have already been published in peer-reviewed journals in the field of forest ecology and soil sciences. The collective synthesis aims at putting the individual publications into the context of the scientific subject of forest site classification, linking them to response strategies to climate change, providing an overview of the methods of spatial statistics and modelling acquired during the doctoral programme, and presenting their scientific relevance as well as conclusions and recommendations for practice. In this regard, each chapter is followed by a brief summary in grey boxes. The detailed study objectives, methodologies, results, discussions, and conclusions are described in the individual publications.

List of publications:

- I Simon, A., Dhendup, K., Rai, P. B., Gratzer, G., 2018. Soil carbon stocks along elevational gradients in Eastern Himalayan mountain forests. *Geoderma Regional* 12: 28-38.
- II Simon, A., Katzensteiner, K., Gratzer, G., 2019. Drivers of forest regeneration patterns in drought prone mixed-species forests in the Northern Calcareous Alps. *Forest Ecology and Management* 453: 117589.
- III Simon, A., Geitner, C., Katzensteiner, K., 2020. A framework for the predictive mapping of forest soil properties in mountain areas. *Geoderma* 371: 114383.
- IV Simon, A., Wilhelmy, M., Klosterhuber, R., Cocuzza, E., Geitner, C., Katzensteiner, K., 2021. A system for classifying subsolum geological substrates as a basis for describing soil formation. *Catena* 198: 105026.

Abstract

The spatial modelling of forest site information is a broad scientific field, ranging from various topics to various scales. In most cases, it is at the interface between forest ecology and other natural sciences, e.g. geology, climatology, botany, soil science, geography, and statistical computing. In any case, the results are essential for sustainable forest management in times of changing environmental conditions. Only detailed knowledge of site ecological conditions enables decisions to be made with regard to tree species or forest management strategies – which will eventually be ‘judged’ by future climate conditions.

Different current topics and methods of forest site classification related to climate change are addressed by the individual publications. These range from the simple forest site classification approach of subdividing mountainous landscapes into vegetation zones along elevational transects (Publication I), individual-based statistical methods for identifying site features driving forest regeneration patterns (Publication II), to the spatial prediction of soil characteristics for forest site information systems (Publications III and IV). Furthermore, different levels of field recordings and modelling scales, from microsites to stand level, are considered. It is common for modern forest site classification systems to use different methodological approaches, but the use and integration of different scales can also help in gaining new insights and recognising patterns that might otherwise not emerge.

In the methodology chapter, an overview of the important statistical methods acquired during the doctoral program is presented. Therein, descriptive statistical analysis formed the basis of all studies and novel methods had to be applied especially for handling the dimensionality of the soil data. To add value to already existing soil analysis data, compiling data from different sources was necessary and required preprocessing and standardisation methods. Besides the modelling itself, assessing accuracy and uncertainty was identified as an essential part of spatial prediction. Therefore, a set of validation methods for model performance, bias, and uncertainty were applied, namely accuracy indices, cross-validation by splitting the dataset with different selections, i.e. either random or spatial block, a description of model uncertainty with estimated prediction intervals, testing for the spatial autocorrelation of the model residuals by applying a sample variogram, and a comparison of the model results of unseen data.

Publication I shows an unimodal distribution of soil organic carbon stock along elevation and indicates a peak in highly productive forest types. Regarding the aspect of climate change mitigation, identifying sites with a high soil organic carbon storage capacity will be of interest. Increasing the proportion of remaining deadwood at such sites could provide effective CO₂ storage. Publication II indicates, that long regeneration periods in combination with suppressed mixed species tree regeneration due to ungulate browsing, will increase the vulnerability of mountain forests growing on Leptosols to climate change. The temporal pattern of the relative growth rate, with a strong decline in 2018, is interpreted as a response to heat waves and drought. In Publication III, the value of newly developed quantitative information on parent material for soil development is shown. This could stimulate further developments in digital

soil mapping, especially in mountain environments. In addition, the characterisation of physical and geochemical soil properties in Publication IV results in practical recommendations for forest management in terms of sustainable biomass use and the risk of soil compaction.

This leads us back to the different aims and purposes of forest site classification, which have in common that they support the sustainable management of forest ecosystems. Herein, the thesis on spatial modelling methods for forest site classification in mountain areas attempts to close the gap between sophisticated statistical methods and practical applications.

Zusammenfassung

Die räumliche Modellierung von Waldstandortsinformationen ist ein breites wissenschaftliches Feld, das sich über verschiedene Themen und Skalen erstreckt. In den meisten Fällen befindet man sich dabei an der Schnittstelle zwischen der Waldökologie und anderen Naturwissenschaften wie z. B. Geologie, Klimatologie, Botanik, Bodenkunde, Geografie und statistischer Datenverarbeitung. In jedem Fall sind die Ergebnisse essenziell für eine nachhaltige Waldbewirtschaftung in Zeiten sich ändernder Umweltbedingungen. Denn nur detaillierte Kenntnisse über die standortökologischen Bedingungen ermöglichen Entscheidungen über Baumarten oder Waldbewirtschaftungsstrategien, die an zukünftigen Klimabedingungen angepasst sind.

In den einzelnen Publikationen der vorliegenden kumulativen Dissertation werden unterschiedliche aktuelle Themen und Methoden der forstlichen Standortskunde in Zusammenhang mit Klimawandel behandelt. Diese reichen vom einfachen Ansatz der Standortskunde, die Landschaft in Bergregionen entlang von Höhen transekten in Vegetationszonen zu unterteilen (Publikation I), über individuenbasierte statistische Methoden zur Identifizierung von Standortmerkmalen, welche Waldverjüngungsmuster bestimmen (Publikation II), bis hin zur räumlichen Vorhersage von Bodeneigenschaften für Standortinformationenssysteme (Publikation III und IV). Darüber hinaus werden verschiedene Ebenen von Feldaufnahmen und Modellierungsskalen - vom Mikrostandort bis hin zur Bestandesebene - berücksichtigt. Die Verwendung verschiedener Skalen kann dazu beitragen, neue Erkenntnisse zu gewinnen und Muster zu erkennen, welche sonst vielleicht verborgen blieben.

Im Methodik-Kapitel wird ein Überblick über die wichtigsten statistischen Verfahren gegeben, die während des Doktoratsstudiums erworben wurden. Die Grundlage aller Untersuchungen bildete dabei die deskriptive statistische Analyse. Um bereits vorhandene Bodenanalysen zu nutzen, war die Zusammenführung aus verschiedenen Quellen notwendig und erforderte Vorbereitungs- und Standardisierungsmethoden. Insbesondere für die Auswertung von mehrdimensionalen Bodendaten wurden neuartige Verfahren angewandt. Neben der eigentlichen Modellierung wurde die Bewertung der Genauigkeit und Unsicherheit als ein wesentlicher Bestandteil der räumlichen Vorhersage identifiziert. Daher kamen eine Reihe von Validierungsmethoden für Modellgenauigkeit, Bias und Unsicherheit zum Einsatz, wie Genauigkeitsindizes, Kreuzvalidierung durch zufällige und räumlich-aggregierte Aufteilung der Daten, Beschreibung der Modellunsicherheit mit geschätzten Prognoseintervallen, Prüfung auf räumliche Autokorrelation der Modellresiduen durch Semivariogramme und Vergleich der Modellergebnisse mit Vorhersagen für unbekannte Daten.

Publikation I zeigt, dass der Kohlenstoffvorrat im Boden einer unimodalen Verteilung mit der Seehöhe folgt und ein Maximum in hochproduktiven Waldgesellschaften aufweist. Unter dem Gesichtspunkt der Abschwächung von negativen Effekten des Klimawandels ist die Identifizierung von Standorten mit hoher Kohlenstoffspeicherkapazität von Interesse. Ein

erhöhter Anteil an verbleibendem Totholz bei der Waldbewirtschaftung könnte dabei zur CO₂-Speicherung an diesen Standorten beitragen. Aus Publikation II ist ersichtlich, dass, in Anbetracht langer Regenerationszeiträume und Baumartenentmischung infolge hoher Verbissintensität durch Schalenwild, die Vulnerabilität von Wäldern auf Rendzinastandorten gegenüber Klimaextremen zunehmen wird. Der zeitliche Verlauf der relativen Wachstumsraten, mit einem starken Rückgang im Jahr 2018, wird als eine Reaktion auf Hitzewellen und Dürre interpretiert. Publikation III beschreibt die Bedeutung quantitativer Information über das Ausgangsmaterial für die Bodenentwicklung. Dies könnte insbesondere in Gebirgsregionen die weitere Entwicklung in der digitalen Bodenmodellierung fördern. Darüber hinaus führt die Charakterisierung physikalischer und geochemischer Bodeneigenschaften in Publikation IV zu praktischen Empfehlungen für die Waldbewirtschaftung in Hinblick auf eine nachhaltige Biomassenutzung und Vermeidung von Bodenverdichtung durch Befahrung.

Dies führt zurück zu den vielfältigen Zielen und unterschiedlichen Zwecken der forstlichen Standortskunde, denen die Unterstützung einer nachhaltigen Bewirtschaftung von Waldökosystemen gemeinsam ist. Dabei versucht die vorliegende Arbeit über räumliche Modellierungsmethoden für die forstliche Standortskunde in Berggebieten, die Lücke zwischen komplexen statistischen Methoden und praktischen Anwendungen zu schließen.

1. Introduction

By presenting basic considerations regarding the idea, development, and trends of forest site classification, the introduction lays the foundation for the topic of the thesis at hand. On this basis, the all-encompassing concept and objectives of the individual publications are presented.

1.1. Forest site classification

1.1.1 Concept of a forest site

There have been many attempts to define the term ‘forest site’, and the aims of ‘forest site classification’ are manifold as well. A location or space that supports tree growth is probably the lowest common denominator for a forest site. This means that the forest site is characterised by the collectivity of abiotic environmental conditions – namely, light, thermal energy, water, nutrient supply, and mechanical factors (e.g. wind, avalanches, slope movement, slope debris, flooding) – that influence tree growth (Arbeitskreis Standortkartierung, 2016). As these primary site factors can hardly be directly measured in the field, they are described by site features as proxies, such as climate conditions, terrain position, physical and chemical soil properties, and vegetation (Englisch and Kilian, 1999). Apart from that, also anthropogenic activities, e.g. through historical land use (Glatzel, 1991) or emissions (Katzensteiner et al., 1992), or successional phases, e.g. as a consequence of natural disturbance regimes (Townsend, 2010), can be considered to further determine the site conditions. With the recognition of ongoing climate change (Auer et al., 2014), the temporal perspective in describing forest sites and their changes has gained increasing attention.

A forest site is a location or space that supports tree growth and is characterised by the collectivity of abiotic environmental conditions influencing tree growth. The temporal perspective of site conditions has recently become more important.

1.1.2 The aims of forest site classification

Based on the presented concept of a forest site, a forest site classification can be seen as the systematics of the ecological features and relationships (Louw and Scholes, 2002), which should stratify and characterise an often complex forest mosaic (Jones, 1994) into homogenous land units. This is in line with Grey (1980), who concluded that a site is an arbitrary subdivision of the environment that should be based as far as possible on ecological principles. Therefore, on the one hand arbitrariness can refer to the gradual changes in the soil, climate, vegetation, and landforms within and between adjacent areas, which entails that the demarcation between site units is within a certain range. On the other hand, arbitrariness can be ascribed to the underlying aim of the classification. According to Rowe (1962), purpose is implicit in all classifications and different purposes lead to different classifications and hence subdivision of

the environment. Nevertheless, the recognition and mapping of the classification units in the field is of particular significance for broad acceptance in practice. Therefore, a site unit is a spatial entity that can be described, classified, recorded, and mapped but cannot be further subdivided without the loss of some intrinsic characteristics (Grey, 1980). These principles are similar to the system hierarchy in landscape ecology with the designation of ecotopes as the smallest ecologically distinct landscape feature (Leser and Löffler, 2017). Besides the subdivision of forestland, another important task of forest site classification is to organise, aggregate, and communicate current and future knowledge and experience about forestland (Jones, 1994). For this reason, in many classification systems the defined site units should have similar silvicultural potential (e.g. recommended tree species, harvesting techniques), similar risks of damage from insects, diseases, or natural hazards, and similar growth and yield of tree species (Barnes et al., 1982). This goes along with the role of decision support tools for forest management. The underlying assumption is that similar forest sites respond in similar ways to management, and that experiences in the past are transferable to the future. Considering the changing environmental conditions, this assumption is under question. In any case, forest site classification has experienced a revitalisation due to ongoing climate change and a golden age of site information is beginning to emerge.

Forest site classification can have multiple aims and different purposes lead to different characterisations and delineations of site units. Therefore, a focus on the silvicultural potential of the site is an inherent aspect of forest site classification.

1.1.3 The evolution of classification approaches

The classification of land as more or less suitable for satisfying human needs is probably as old as mankind itself and by far exceeds written records (Roth, 1916). The first documented attempts at the classification of natural resources in forestry date back to the early 18th century (Hartig, 1847). In the decades that followed, the importance of different forest site characteristics, mainly soil moisture and climate, for tree growth was recognised (Ramann, 1893; Vater, 1916; Krauss, 1936). Nevertheless, the focus was on yield optimisation, and productivity indicators, e.g. increment (Bates, 1918) or height growth (Roth, 1916; Watson, 1917) were postulated as the only criteria. No doubt, this is important information that should be provided by comprehensive forest site classification. Nevertheless, productivity indicators are dependent variables of the forest site and describe rather the state than its intrinsic characteristics. These are neither transferable in time and space nor applicable to different tree species and vegetation types.

The principle of characterising forest sites by classifying the vegetation was also amongst the first approaches. The different schools of phytosociology e.g. the “Zürich-Montpellier-School” of Braun Blanquet (1928), the “Finish School” of Cajander (1930), and the “Russian School” of Morozov (1912), are examples of such vegetation-based approaches. A

phytosociological approach has the advantage that with botanical knowledge and experience the units are easy to identify and map in the field. However, vegetation is also a dependent variable of the primary site factors and strongly depends on the factor of light. It can change for a specific site between successional stages or management regimes quite dramatically. A pure phytosociological approach also does not provide a possibility for further subdivision in the absence of character species. As an example, the vegetation relevées that Oberdorfer et al. (1992) used to describe the species-poor association *Vaccinio-Abietetum* expand between 350 m to 1,190 m a.s.l. and appear to be suitable for *Quercus robur* at least at lower elevations, while this tree species does not occur at higher elevations. Therefore, an important prerequisite, i.e. similar silvicultural potential in terms of choice of tree species (Barnes et al., 1982), for practical forest site classification is not fulfilled.

For the transition from site classification based on dependent variables to the consideration of the independent predictor variables of forest sites, the work of Jenny (1941) and Major (1951) represent cornerstones. However, a similar hypothesis was already formulated by the Russian soil scientists Dukachev in 1886 and Zakharov in 1927 (Florinsky, 2012) but remained largely undetected in the English language literature. Each of them identified climate, parent material for soil formation, relief, organisms including humans, and time as the independent drivers of soil and vegetation development, which also mutually interact, but more in a co-evolutional than determinative manner. The recognition of these factors has given rise to the development of numerous site classification systems based on a multi-factorial approach using site features such as climate, terrain position (e.g. landforms, aspect, inclination), physical and chemical soil properties, and vegetation. The combined systems approach replaced single-factor systems for most applications.

In Central Europe the transition from forest site descriptions to a systematic forest site classification was initiated in the 1920ies to 1930ies (Fiedler, 1989). During that time, fundamental works were written on the subject by Gustav Krauss (Krauss, 1936; Krauss et al., 1939). His ideas contributed to the development of the multi-factorial approach forest site classification (Rodenkirchen, 2009), and the identified site features are still used in numerous classification systems (Arbeitskreis Standortkartierung, 2016). This also includes the combination of soil types and soil parent material (“Bodenformen”) (AD-HOC-Arbeitsgruppe Boden, 2005) and the development of ecological soil substrate groups (Fig. 1) to combine soil morphology, pedogenesis and soil parent material. There is also a direct link to current methods in digital soil mapping (Publication III and IV) and forest site classification systems in mountain regions (e.g. Forest Site Classification Tyrol (2018)), which utilise subsolum geological substrates to describe soil formation. A thorough review of the development of forest site classification in the German-speaking region from its origins to modern times is presented by Fiedler (1989).

In the North American literature, a multi-factorial approach including vegetation and soil is often called ecological site classification (Barnes et al., 1982). Ecological site classification refined the physiographical approach of Hills (1953), which was widely used for forest site

classification in Canada. Emphasising physiography for classification benefited from the use of aerial photographs to also map inaccessible areas. In the physiographical approach, the vegetation is not considered to be stable and can develop from a pioneer stage through intermediate stages to a climax or less disturbed stage (Burger, 1972). The inclusion of forest disturbances and the concept of successional stages or phases (e.g. a state-and-transition model) for site units is still a vital component of forest site classification in North America (Townsend, 2010). This concept may also be helpful in addressing points of criticisms and increasing the practical relevance of the concept of potential natural vegetation (Tüxen, 1956), which provided the guidelines for numerous classification systems in Europe, e.g. Ellenberg and Klötzli (1972) for Switzerland, Walentowski et al. (2004) for Bavaria in Germany, and the Forest Site Classification South Tyrol (2010) in Italy.

The introduction of site regions (Hills, 1960) in which the physiographical features come into effect can also be seen as the implementation of a multi-level classification system (Arbeitskreis Standortkartierung, 2016). A multi-level approach with a landscape and local (~stand) level (Fig. 1) is still deemed to be up to date and widely used internationally. For example, it is reflected in the biogeoclimatic ecosystem classification of British Columbia, Canada (Meidinger and Pojar, 1991), in several federal states of Germany (Arbeitskreis Standortkartierung, 2016), and is also recommended for Austria (Englisch and Kilian, 1999), where the first classification of forest growth regions (Wuchsgebiete) was published in the 1960s (Tschermak, 1953). In contrast, a single-level approach directly combines site features, e.g. climate, vegetation, topographic position, and soil, to derive the site units. Therein the scaling of the site features is constant over the whole application area (the modelling extent) and the site unit is valid on a supra-regional level. With the increasing implementation of spatial prediction models for forest site classification and high computing power, the role of a multi-level approach might recede into the background. Regarding such, the categorisation of new approaches and their relation to existing ones will become more apparent during their implementation.

Figure 1: Multi-level site classification approach. Modified from Arbeitskreis Standortskartierung (2016, p.273).

As another categorisation of land and resource classification systems, the differences between taxonomic and regionalisation approaches are discussed by Bailey et al. (1978). A pure taxonomic approach is described as place-independent and strives for the aggregation of sites with similar properties, while a regionalisation approach as a mapping procedure is always object-dependent and aims to subdivide sites with different properties. These approaches offer alternative ways to deal with the same resource and can both implement single-factor or multi-factorial as well as single-level or multi-level approaches. In addition, these categories are not mutually exclusive and might complement each other in many classification systems. A new forest site classification could start with the stratification of the environment, which is in the domain of regionalisation, to obtain an optimal distribution of sampling points. The information of the sampling points can then be used to build up a taxonomic classification, and these again could build the basis for mapping in the field. This example demonstrates that the use of

The recognition of independent predictor variables for soil and vegetation has fostered multi-factorial approaches to site classification. These ecological site classification systems use mainly site features such as climate, terrain position, physical and chemical soil properties, and vegetation.

A multi-level approach with landscape and local levels is widely used internationally. With the increasing implementation of spatial prediction models for forest site classification and high computing power, the use of a multi-level approach might recede into the background. The use of different approaches is common in modern forest site classification systems.

different approaches is common in modern forest site classification systems and the borders between systems are diminishing.

1.1.4 Current topics of forest site research

Since the 1990s two trends have changed the field of forest site classification quite dramatically, i.e. the rapid development of computer-based geographic information system (GIS) technology (Burger and Pierpoint, 1990) and a combination thereof with models from other domains (Jones, 1994). In the latter, empirical models, spatial prediction models, and process-based models are used in forest site classification. Forest site mapping established on data-based sets of classification rules (Forest Site Classification Tyrol, 2018) or the application of pedo-transfer functions to legacy soil profiles (Publication III) to quantify the plant-available water storage capacity (PAWC) are examples of the use of empirical models. The spatial prediction of continuous information on site features, e.g. through methods of digital soil mapping (McBratney et al., 2003), has also found application in the field of forest site classification (Publication III). The integration of process-based models such as hydrological models (Schwärzel et al., 2009; Gauer et al., 2011) or dynamic vegetation models (Bugmann, 2001) are the last stages of model integration, but will certainly not be the end of such development.

Considering the temperature increase trend and related climatic extremes in the Greater Alpine Area (Auer et al., 2014) and the continuous trend of increasing global carbon emissions (Le Quéré et al., 2018), mountain forests are likely to undergo dramatic change in the coming centuries (Allen et al., 2010). Therefore, finding answers to urgent questions as to the impacts of and possible adaptation to climate change is one of the current challenges of forest site classification. The dynamic modelling of site features that determine the characteristics of forest sites or of individual species behaviour are therefore the most promising approaches.

Most closely connected to classical forest site classification is the prediction of climate-sensitive site features, above all the soil water budget and drought stress (Puhlmann et al., 2019) and thermal elevation zones of vegetation (Reger et al., 2011; Riek et al., 2013; Huber et al., 2019). There is little doubt about the suitability of these approaches, in contrast to correlative species distribution models (SDM). Regarding the latter, attention should be devoted to the following: susceptibility to bias due to incomplete spatial coverage of the true distribution of species (Guisan et al., 2017); the definition, availability, and reliability of absence data; variable selection and scale (Austin and van Niel, 2010), the compensatory effect of variables at the distribution margins of species (Mellert et al., 2018); the intraspecific physiological variation of different provenances, as shown by Wang et al. (2020) for seedlings of European beech; and missing links to ecological theory (Austin, 2007). Nevertheless, correlative SDMs are widely used in ecology and conservation, but are also suggested for tree species recommendations (Falk and Mellert, 2011); for a review on applications in forest management, see Pecchi et al. (2019). Besides modelling individual species distributions, also climate-based modelling

approaches for entire vegetation types, i.e. site units, exist (Fischer et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2020). A completely different approach pursues mechanistic or process-based models, which most often focus on only a limited dimensionality of forest ecosystems, e.g. physiological processes in physiological models, structural and compositional processes in gap models, or spatial complexity in landscape models. Therefore, forest gap models and hybrids of physiological and gap models have been applied in numerous climate change impact assessments in mountain forests (Lexer et al., 2002; Rasche et al., 2011; Irauschek et al., 2017; Thrippleton et al., 2020). The application of such climate-sensitive forest dynamic models to specific forest site units is a promising approach for evaluating tree species recommendations in circumstances of changing site features.

In addition to dynamic modelling, also static approaches to inevitable issues regarding changing site conditions are being implemented. For example, analogue-climate vegetation (Kölling and Zimmermann, 2014) is being identified in order to make inferences regarding future tree species compositions, and adaptive ecograms are being developed (Frehner et al., 2019) for the assessment of climate-induced shifts in site units. These approaches can be seen as temporary adaptations in the process of transition from static to dynamic modelling in forest site classification.

GIS technology and the combination thereof with empirical models, spatial prediction models, and process models have boosted developments in forest site classification.

Finding answers to urgent questions as to the impacts of and possible adaptation to climate change is one of the current challenges of forest site classification. The dynamic modelling of the site features that determine the characteristics of forest sites and species behaviour is therefore the most promising approach, but also temporary adaptations of existing systems can support decision-making.

1.2. Concept and objectives

The overall aim of this cumulative thesis is to develop, implement, and evaluate spatial modelling methods for forest site classification in mountain areas. Herein, different current topics of forest site classification related to climate change are considered (Fig. 2). Furthermore, the individual publications address different levels of spatial scale, defined by observation scale, modelling scale, and modelling extent. For this purpose, the different modelling scales are defined as micro-scale, meso-scale, and macro-scale, providing information on microsite, stand, hillslope, landscape, or regional level. In accordance with the proposed categorisation of the modelling scale, the modelling extent is defined as covering sections of the environment at microsite, stand, hillslope, landscape, and regional levels. A description of the determined scales and extent levels is given in Table 1 (Chapter 3.1).

Figure 2: Conceptual model of the relationship between the impact of climate change, response strategies, and the objectives of the thesis.

Publication I showed that with simple methods of forest site classification, by subdividing mountainous landscapes into vegetation zones along elevational transects, the site features of an under-explored forestland, such as an Eastern Himalayan mountain forest, can be characterised. This is demonstrated for soil carbon stock and soil types along elevational gradients in consideration of forest vegetation zones. Addressing the largest terrestrial sink for organic carbon (Batjes, 1996), Publication I is directly connected to strategies for mitigating (Fig. 2) climate change impacts (IPCC, 2014). The quantification of soil organic carbon and the characterisation of forest soil properties along elevational transects on individual hill slopes in the temperate conifer forests of Western and Central Bhutan were made at a hillslope extent, with the results (modelling scale) valid at a meso-scale (stand).

In Publication II, the drivers of forest regeneration patterns in drought prone mixed-species forests in the Northern Calcareous Alps were studied. At the study site, shallow soil, in combination with steep slopes and high incident solar radiation on sun-exposed aspects, imply severe conditions for tree regeneration. Factors negatively affecting the establishment and growth of seedlings are drought stress, overheating, limited nutrient availability, and competition with herbaceous vegetation (Burschel et al., 1992; Ammer, 1996; Pröll et al., 2015; Pröll et al., 2016). With the ongoing climate change, it is likely that the conditions for successful

regeneration will further deteriorate at these sites. Hence, investigating the relation between regeneration patterns and site conditions is crucial for evaluating the impacts of climate change (Fig. 2) on recent and future forest vulnerability and management (Fig. 2). The observation and modelling scale are on a micro-scale with 0.5 m resolution, while the extent is at stand level, with study sites of approx. 225 to 250 m².

Besides mitigation, adaptation is the second pillar in the response to climate change impacts on forest ecosystems. In order to support the successful adaptation of forest ecosystems through management, detailed site information, especially on soil properties, is required (Manusch et al., 2014; Jönsson and Lagergren, 2018; Mellert et al., 2018). Information on soil properties at a sufficient resolution to be incorporated into spatially explicit models is, however, rare, in particular for mountain forest areas which are poorly accessible and where sampling effort is high. In order to bridge this gap, a concept for predicting spatially continuous forest soil properties in mountain areas was developed (Publication III). With application to the forest area of the federal state of Tyrol in Austria, which covers approximately 513,000 ha of mountain forest (Gruppe Forst, 2018), the modelling extent is at a regional level, while the modelling scale, with a 5 m spatial resolution, is still at micro-scale.

The need for characterisation of the parent material for soil formation at the interface between the disciplines of geology and soil science emerged from Publication III. Hence, Publication IV describes the development of a novel geochemical-physical classification system for subsolum geological substrates as a basis for both understanding soil formation and modelling soil properties. This research topic addresses the quantitative description of parent material as an important predictor in forest site characterisation and consequently also for forest ecosystems that are influenced by climate change (Fig. 2). With the restrictive spatial scale of the geological maps used (1:25,000 to 15,000) (GBA, 2019) as the basis, the modelling scale is at the finer granularity of the meso-scale. The application scale of the presented approach is currently at the regional extent, but due to the openness of the proposed classification system for further differentiation, it is transferable to the entire Alpine arc and other mountain regions. Therefore, it could also be applied to a national or international (ecozone level) extent, as proposed by Kolb and Göttlein (2019).

Different current topics of forest site classification related to climate change were addressed by the individual publications of this cumulative thesis. Furthermore, different modelling scales, from micro-scale to meso-scale, and different modelling extents of site features, from stand to regional level, were considered.

2. Methodology

The methodology is presented with regard to the primarily applied methods. It should not repeat the content of the publications; rather, it provides an overview of the datasets used and important methods acquired during the doctoral program. For a detailed description of the methodology, it refers to the respective publications.

2.1. Descriptive and classification methods

In Publication I, mainly descriptive statistical methods were used for the quantification of soil organic carbon and forest soil characteristics along elevational transects. The analysed data consist of 82 soil profile descriptions according to FAO (2006). The profiles were examined, in steps of 100 m of elevation along six elevational transects, ranging from 2,600 to 4,000 m a.s.l. Out of all of the described soil profiles, 19 profiles representative of the different soil types were selected. Out of these, 66 samples were taken for chemical and physical analysis. Recordings of tree and shrub vegetation at each sampling site completed this dataset. For the descriptive analysis of soil data, the statistical software R (R Core Team, 2019) with the package: 'Algorithms for Quantitative Pedology' (aqp) of Beaudette et al. (2013) was used.

Likewise, descriptive statistical methods for soil data were used in Publication IV. In order to describe and evaluate the influence of the subsolum geological substrate (SSGS) classification units on soil formation and soil properties, a compilation of data from 389 soil profile analyses of Tyrolean forests was used. The dataset is continuously expanded with further sampling and analysis, to supplement the information on infrequent classification units. Since the data used were from different sources, the sampling was carried out either according to genetic soil horizons or fixed depth intervals. Therefore, standardisation methods were applied to calculate the average chemical properties of the depth intervals. The calculation was made by assigning the analysis results to slices of 1 cm thickness, aggregating them according to the depth intervals and calculating summary statistics. Furthermore, an SSGS classification system was developed. This is based on the mineral component groups of the subsolum geological substrates, namely dolomite and calcite, as well as felsic, mafic, and clay minerals. The categorisation was implemented in three distinct triangular diagrams with a scope of application according to the proportion of carbonate. The final encoding of the SSGS units consists of three entities describing the lithogenetic, geochemical, and physical properties. The practical application included the processing and classification of geological reference samples and was applied to 321 analysed field samples of unconsolidated deposits.

Descriptive statistical analysis forms the basis of most scientific studies and is a prerequisite for further analyses. To add value to the already existing soil analysis data, compiling data from different sources is usually necessary and requires preprocessing and standardisation methods.

2.2. Spatial and individual-based methods

Spatial point process modelling, as an individual-based method (Pommerening and Grabarnik, 2019), was applied in Publication II. For this study, the spatially explicit tree regeneration data of two fenced plots of 245 m² and 223 m² were used. For investigating the underlying processes, a nonstationary Poisson point process model (Baddeley et al., 2015) was fitted to the observed point pattern. In the event of unexplained clustering, a Thomas cluster point process model as a special case of the Neyman-Scott process (Velázquez et al., 2016) was fitted. The fitted point process model and the cluster point process model were used to create a nonstationary parametric intensity function, which was used as the basis for the null hypothesis (Law et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2011) for further analysis. The influence of the spatial covariates, global site factor (gsf), rock outcrop, saga wetness index (swi), distance to mature trees, seed density, and competition were tested. Covariates were selected based on potential driving factors of tree regeneration: the light environment (gsf) as regards its direct effect on photosynthesis, as well as the indirect influence on soil moisture and the heating of the ecto-organic humus layer and topsoil; rock outcrops as catchers of precipitation that would create moist spots in their neighbourhood; swi as the microrelief specification to account for improved soil moisture and seed accumulation; distance to mature trees for interactions with the heterospecifics either facilitating or inhibiting germination and growth; seed availability as an essential and often limiting factor for successful regeneration; and competition with already established tree regeneration describing the availability of resources. The first and second order processes were analysed with a pair correlation function (Stoyan and Stoyan, 1994), because it is non-cumulative (Wiegand and Moloney, 2004; Perry et al., 2006; Law et al., 2009) and proved to be robust to pattern idiosyncrasies (Wiegand et al., 2013). The confidence envelopes were calculated with a 99-fold Monte Carlo simulation of complete spatial randomness (Baddeley et al., 2015). For the edge correction, the translation-corrected estimate was used. This method has proven to be a suitable method to reduce errors due to edge effects (Pommerening and Stoyan, 2006). The interactions between regeneration patterns of different species and height classes were assessed with cross-pair correlation function (Baddeley et al., 2015) summary statistics.

Spatial and individual-based methods are powerful tools for analysing the underlying patterns in forest ecology and small-scale tree species distribution. Defining an appropriate null hypothesis for the assumed point process is a crucial step in the analysis.

2.3. Regression-based and machine learning methods

In Publication III, a concept for predicting spatially continuous forest soil properties in mountain areas was developed and substantiated by comparing two statistical approaches to digital soil mapping (DSM). The differences between machine learning algorithms, such as Random Forests, and regression-based models, such as Generalized Additive Models (GAM), were investigated. On the one hand, Random Forests is a classifier consisting of a collection of tree-structured classifiers, whereby each tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently with the same distribution for all trees (Breiman, 2001). On the other hand, GAM is a semi-parametric generalisation of linear regression models (Wood, 2017), which use thin plate regression splines to account for non-linear relationships. The focus was on the prediction of the plant-available water storage capacity (PAWC), as an important physical soil property, and Ellenberg's ecological indicator values (Ellenberg et al., 2001) for soil reaction to characterise chemical soil properties. The study used field descriptions of 1,653 legacy soil profiles from the Tyrol Forest Site Classification project (Forest Site Classification Tyrol, 2018) sampled between 2003 and 2018. The georeferenced sampling sites (GPS recorded and post-corrected with the Digital Terrain Model) range from 485 to 2,120 m a.s.l. and are evenly distributed over the Tyrolian forestland. At each sampling site, general information on the topography and geological substrate was recorded according to Englisch and Kilian (1999) and a soil pit was excavated and described in line with the Austrian soil taxonomy (Nestroy et al., 2000, 2011). Furthermore, the cover-abundance of vascular species according to a modified Braun-Blanquet scale was recorded within a homogenous 400 m² plot on a nine-class ordinal scale according to van der Maarel (1979). A set of 23 spatially explicit predictor variables, grouped into geological substrate information, topography, climate, biotic, and time-space, was tested for predictive power. Thus, in Publication III there was a special focus on the predictive value of the newly developed geological substrate maps, which include lithogenetic units, lithological composition, and the multilayering of sediments. For the evaluation of both statistical approaches, a set of validation methods for model performance, bias, and uncertainty was applied, namely accuracy indices (e.g. the squared Pearson correlation coefficient (r^2), the mean squared error skill score (SS_{mse})), cross-validation by splitting the dataset with different selections, i.e. either random or spatial block (Valavi et al., 2019), a description of the model uncertainty with estimated prediction intervals (Malone et al., 2011), testing for the spatial autocorrelation of the model residuals by applying a sample variogram (Bivand et al., 2008), and a comparison of the model results of unseen data.

The preprocessing and standardisation of soil data and the derivation of response and predictor variables represent a significant workload in digital soil mapping. Applying different methods for evaluating model performance, bias, and uncertainty is an essential part of spatial prediction.

3. Results and Discussion

The results and discussion are presented with regard to the spatial extent of the modelling results. It recapitulates the important findings of the publications that comprise this thesis, but also shows unpublished data and analyses, the results of ongoing studies, and practical applications. For the detailed results and discussion, please refer to the respective publications.

3.1. Modelling scale and extent

Considerations of scale and extent are an important methodological issue in ecology (Levin, 1992) as well as in forest site classification. The most prominent aspect of scale in modelling is the effect of resolution, but the effect of extent, in terms of the size of the study area, might also play an important role, especially in species distribution models when it comes to the investigation of the fully realised environmental niche of a species. In terms of resolution, spatial (e.g. cell size), thematic (e.g. the number of different categories), and temporal (e.g. the appropriate reference period of the climate data) information can be distinguished (Guisan et al., 2017).

Table 1: A description of the determined spatial modelling scale and extent. *Italic letters*: examples not addressed by the thesis; the range size indication refers to the raster side length or maximum expansion.

range	modelling scale		modelling extent	
	scale	application	level	application
0.5 to 10 m	micro	Publication II Publication III	microsite	<i>windthrow plate</i> <i>pit-mound relief</i>
10 to 500 m	meso I	Publication I Publication IV	(patch) stand	Publication II
500 to $5 \cdot 10^3$ m	meso II	<i>regional</i> <i>climate</i> <i>models</i> <i>various</i>	hillslope	Publication I
$5 \cdot 10^3$ to $50 \cdot 10^3$ m	macro I	<i>national</i> <i>monitoring</i> <i>grids</i>	landscape	<i>forest growth</i> <i>district</i>
$50 \cdot 10^3$ to $25 \cdot 10^4$ m	macro II	<i>global climate</i> <i>models</i>	regional	Publication III Publication IV
$25 \cdot 10^4$ to $15 \cdot 10^5$ m	mega	-	ecozone	<i>Alpine arc</i>

Herein, the individual publications of this cumulative thesis address different levels of spatial scale. A description of the determined scales and extent levels is given in Table 1. However, various disciplines of forestry science, e.g. plant ecology, disturbance ecology, forest hydrology, and forest management, use different spatial scale classification systems. The applied terminology and delineation (Table 1) follow the landscape ecology approaches of Leser and Löffler (2017) and the integrated concepts of disturbance ecology (Wohlgemuth et al., 2019), and apply them to forest site classification. From the different allocation of the publications between modelling scale and extent, the decoupling of modelling scales from modelling extent due to digital mapping becomes obvious. This is fostered by the increase in computing power, which allows modelling at a regional extent, with the micro- to meso-scale spatial resolution of predictor variables. In any case, the spatial extent and modelling scale should fit the sampling point density, the spatial autocorrelation of the response variable, the spatial resolution of the predictor variables, and the underlying scale of the processes involved. If the modelling scale is too coarse, fine-scale variability often smooths out as the spatial extent increases. On the other hand, non-existing spatial variability or accuracy is implied if the modelling scale is a magnitude higher than the important predictor variables (e.g. climate, geology) or the sampling density is low compared to the modelling extent.

In general, models that use coarse spatial resolution show high model fit even in the event they are ecologically problematic (Guisan et al., 2017). Therefore, an increase in resolution does not always result in higher accuracy and model performance. Nevertheless, finer-grained information may identify correlations that smooth out at the coarse grain level. For example, Randin et al. (2009) demonstrated that local-scaled models predict the persistence of suitable habitats for plant species under conditions of climate change, where European-scale models predict extinction. Furthermore, many patterns emerge only at a certain scale and are ascribed to noise or constants, or are not even recognised at other scales (Chave, 2013). According to Levin (1992), there is no single natural scale at which ecological phenomena should be studied, because systems show characteristic variability across a range of spatial, temporal, and organisational scales. For these reasons, a combination of different spatial modelling scales (meso-scale and micro-scale), extents (ecozone and landscape/regional levels), and temporal scales in hierarchical frameworks (Keil et al., 2013; Talluto et al., 2016) are promising approaches to the further development of modelling forest site classifications.

Considerations of scale and extent are an important methodological issue in forest ecology and site classification. Many patterns emerge only at a certain scale and are ascribed to noise or constants, or are not even recognised at other scales.

The decoupling of the spatial extent from the spatial resolution of predictor variables is fostered by the increase in computing power. This allows modelling at a regional extent, with the micro- to meso-scale spatial resolution of predictor variables.

Nevertheless, the spatial extent and the modelling scale should fit the sampling point density, the spatial autocorrelation of the response variable, i.e. soil properties, the spatial resolution of the predictor variables, and the underlying scale of the processes involved.

3.2. Stand-level forest regeneration patterns

In the temperate mountain forests of the Calcareous Alps, shallow soils, in combination with steep slopes and high radiation input on sun-exposed slopes, are site features that imply severe conditions for tree regeneration. The aim of Publication II was to understand the influence of these site features and other drivers of forest regeneration patterns. Therein, regeneration was associated with higher shading, safe sites close to *Fagus sylvatica* (L.), and protection from ungulate browsing. In order to also capture the temporal scale of tree regeneration dynamics, data recording continued after 2018 at the study sites and currently comprises eight successive years. The recent state of regeneration of the three main tree species is presented in Figure 3. In the fenced plots (Fig. 3A, Fig. 3C) the development of regeneration is continuous, with a steady increase in the density of taller height classes for all species. In contrast to the fenced plots, the unfenced plots (Fig. 3B, Fig. 3D) still show no change in density and height of regeneration.

Figure 3: Development of regeneration over eight years in different height classes for the main tree species. A: upper site, fenced plot; B: upper site, unfenced plot; C: lower site, fenced plot; D: lower site, unfenced plot.

For all three main tree species, namely Norway spruce (*Picea abies* ((L.) Karst)), European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* (L.)), and Silver fir (*Abies alba* (MILL.)), individuals did not grow higher than 30 cm (Fig. 3). Also, for the relatively browsing-resistant species *Picea abies*, no progression could be observed. The results clearly show that the current browsing level successfully prevents tree species regeneration. Furthermore, it reduces tree species richness and simplifies forest composition and structure (Rackham, 2008), which may cause reduced resilience and higher vulnerability with respect to climate change.

Figure 4: Volumetric water content at a soil depth of 5 cm at ten measurement locations in the upper study site. The numbers are successive days with VWC below 30%; orange areas indicate potential drought stress at the measured soil depth.

Considering the long regeneration periods of the studied forest type, significantly reduced game density is necessary for at least two decades to ensure the successive regeneration of all three main tree species.

The results of the continuous measurement of the volumetric water content (VWC) at a soil depth of 5 cm since the summer of 2016 are shown in Figure 4. At the beginning of the measurements, only 5 sensors were installed, while in the summer of 2018 the measuring network was intensified to include more microsites and to better cover the spatial variability. Differences at the micro-scale become obvious by comparing the VWC time series. Measurement point 1 (Fig. 4) showed by far the highest VWC and is next to a decomposed tree stump. In comparison, measurement points 4 and 6 are at the dry end of the measurements and represent microsites at the forest gap edge with crown cover and at the same time high radiation input (gsf) due to aspect and inclination. The differences in measurements substantiate the importance of micro-scale approaches in capturing the drivers of tree regeneration patterns.

The number of successive drought days in Figure 4 clearly indicate the drought event of 2018, which was omnipresent in Central Europe (Krejza et al., 2020). The measurements also reveal the regular occurrences of drought in the spring months, despite generally high mean annual precipitation and snow cover.

Figure 5: Annual relative growth rates of the most common tree species. The numbers indicate the number of individual plants.

As is obvious from Figure 5, the relative growth rate of the main tree species showed a sharp decline in 2018, which matches a drought event in that year (Fig. 4). Only *Pinus sylvestris*, which is known to be highly drought-tolerant (Krakau et al., 2013), showed no decline in the relative growth rate for the measurement period 2018-2019. These results are interpreted as evidencing a high level of vulnerability of the study site to heat waves and drought. Hence,

investigating micro-scale, drought-related patterns of tree regeneration is crucial for recent and future forest management. By identifying the vulnerability of forest sites and quantifying the site-specific impact (Fig. 2) of climate change, the management strategies can be implemented in a more focused manner.

High browsing intensity will increase vulnerability to climate change due to suppressed mixed species tree regeneration. Considering the long regeneration periods of mountain forests growing on Leptosols, significantly reduced game density is necessary for at least two decades to ensure the successive regeneration of all three main tree species.

The spatial variability of the predisposition to drought of the sites reveals the importance of micro-scale approaches to capturing the drivers of tree regeneration patterns.

The temporal pattern of the relative growth rate, with a strong decline in 2018, is interpreted as the study site having high vulnerability to heat waves and drought, and therefore to climate change impacts.

3.3. Hillslope-level forest soil characteristics

The soil profiles of two representative elevational transects from Publication I are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The transects are approximately 10 km away from each other, span from the broadleaf to the cold conifer vegetation zone in Central Bhutan, and cover an elevation range from 2,600 m to 4,000 m a.s.l. The soil types range from Fluvisol at valley bottoms, followed by different types of Cambisols (Haplic, Stagnic, Dystric), to Podzols. Despite the generally high variability of soils in mountain areas and the limited number of soil profiles in Publication I, clear relationships between vegetation types and soils were observed. Phaeozems occurred only under drier site conditions in the cool conifer zone, Stagnosols were most prominent at intermediate elevation, and Podzols were restrained to high elevation and affiliated with the cold conifer zone.

Figure 6: The elevational gradient of soil profiles from broadleaf to cool conifer moist vegetation zones. Location: Chokhortoe transect I, Central Bhutan.

Figure 7: The elevational gradient of soil profiles from cool conifer moist to cold conifer vegetation zones. Location: Dhur transect 1, Central Bhutan.

Similar vegetation-soil relationships were observed for the recorded soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks, up to a depth of 100 cm, which ranged between 56.7 and 337.8 $\text{Mg} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$. Along the elevational gradient, the soils showed a unimodal curve for SOC stock with a peak between 3,200 and 3,400 m a.s.l. (Fig. 8). The soil profiles with SOC analysis of the two transects are highlighted in Figure 8, these are 1st, 5th, 7th, and 9th profiles in Figure 6 and the 2nd and 6th profiles in Figure 7 (left to right). They very well represent the unimodal pattern of total data with similar values at the peak, which agree with the upper range of the cool conifer moist forest. This vegetation zone not only has the highest SOC, with a max. of 337.8 $\text{Mg} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$ (mean: $206.1 \pm 105 \text{ Mg} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$), but also remarkably high aboveground carbon storage in the biomass (Wangda and Ohsawa, 2006; Wangdi et al., 2017).

The subsequent decrease in SOC stocks is explained by shallow soils and the reduced net primary productivity (NPP) of the forest types at higher elevation. The observed pattern is interpreted as being a manifestation of changes in temperature and precipitation with elevation. Nevertheless, reduced SOC stocks could have a negative feedback on the NPP, as an example of the influence of soil organic matter on forest productivity shown by Grigal and Vance (2000). The relationship between vegetation and soil is seen as a mutual influence and the factors are not independent of each other. The importance of vegetation-soil interactions for soil development and hence forest site classification as discussed in the introduction (Chapter 1.1.3) were confirmed by Publication I.

Figure 8: Soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks at elevation classes. Points = median, red circles = the sample points of Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. The numbers indicate the number of profiles.

Considering the observed high SOC stocks in deeply weathered soils, with highly productive forests and low anthropogenic impacts, under the aspect of climate change mitigation (Fig. 2), conclusions can be drawn also for other mountain areas. Leaving deadwood, or the active enrichment thereof, has the potential to increase the SOC stocks of forests and their sink effect on CO₂ emissions. This might be especially true for highly productive forests, which commonly experience the highest exploitation rates and show the lowest amount of deadwood (BFW, 2019). Therefore, an increased proportion of deadwood at sites with high storage capacities in the soil and slow decomposition rates (Wambsganss et al., 2017) will be an effective CO₂ storage. Higher C sequestration of aboveground forest biomass and wood products at more productive (higher site index) forest sites was also detected by Nunery and Keeton (2010). Moreover, they demonstrated the advantages of silvicultural systems with high structural retention in terms of C sequestration, which is also likely to facilitate higher amounts of deadwood and SOC. In addition, higher SOC stocks could also have a positive feedback on forest productivity and reduced vulnerability to climate change. The appropriate sites could be identified with the help of forest site classification.

The soil organic carbon stock showed a unimodal distribution along elevation and indicated a peak in highly productive forests. The relationship between vegetation and soil is seen as a mutual influence as the factors are not independent of each other. Under the aspect of climate change mitigation, an increased proportion of deadwood at sites with high net primary productivity can provide effective CO₂ storage.

3.4. Regional-level predictive forest soil mapping

The publication on digital soil mapping (Publication III) and the publication on classifying subsolum geological substrates (Publication IV) both cover, with application to the federal state of Tyrol, a regional modelling extent. Furthermore, they both share an important basis, namely the geological maps and derivatives thereof. The early recognition of parent material as an important factor in soil formation by Dokuchaev and Zakhorav (Florinsky, 2012) as well as Jenny (1941) has already been discussed in the introduction (Chapter 1.1.3). Thus, quantitative information on the lithogenetic, geochemical, and physical characteristics of subsolum geological substrates (Publication IV) are essential input parameters for digital soil mapping (Publication III).

Topography and associated morphometric terrain features are formative characteristics of mountain areas and, due to their various effects on redistribution processes, as well as on the water and energy budgets of forest sites, are deemed to be the most essential soil forming factors. Thus, variables derived from Digital Terrain Models (DTMs), which are available in high spatial resolution, are assumed to be one of the most important predictors in digital soil mapping. For this reason, a modelling scale of 5 x 5 m (micro-scale) was selected, being aware that only the derivatives of the DTM have an initial resolution finer than that.

In contrast, a review by Grunwald (2009) stated that information on the parent material was used in less than 10% of digital soil mapping studies. However, the importance of parent material for digital soil mapping in mountain areas was clearly confirmed by the prediction models for the plant-available water storage capacity (PAWC). For that physical soil property, the predictor variables related to subsolum geological substrates (SSGS) account for around 76% of the variance explained. In general, it was possible to predict the PAWC with a significant degree of accuracy, with $r^2 = 0.49-0.56$. The results of the spatial prediction are shown in Figure 9. Furthermore, Ellenberg's indicator value of vegetation turned out to be a suitable proxy for soil pH value, and was modelled with a high degree of predictive power, with $r^2=0.75-0.77$. While for the biologically driven state variable organic humus layer thickness, an r^2 of only 0.22-0.27 was achieved. In summary, the proposed modelling approach is able to provide response variables to characterise physical and chemical soil properties in high resolution and sufficient quality. Nevertheless, the thickness of the organic layer, as a highly variable and biologically driven state variable, turned out to be difficult to model without information on the historical vegetation cover, tree species distribution, forest management, and land use. All of the studied soil properties are important site information for the adaptation of forest ecosystems to climate change (Fig. 2). Chemical soil properties determine tree species suitability (Mellert et al., 2020); humus layer thickness acts as a rhizosphere and water storage (Hajnos et al., 2003), and is a potential greenhouse gas source of forest ecosystems (Mayer et al., 2017); and especially PAWC is a key property as it quantifies the amount of water available for plants that the soil can store (Arbeitskreis Standortskartierung, 2016) and therefore balances precipitation and drought events.

Figure 9: Prediction of the plant available water storage capacity (PAWC) up to a depth of 100 cm.

Moreover, the results of Publication III show that the spatial modelling extent is independent of the spatial resolution (modelling scale) of the predictor variables (Table 1). This decoupling is fostered by the increasing amount of computing power, which enables modelling at a regional extent, with the micro- to meso-scale spatial resolution of the predictor variables. In the presented case of digital soil mapping at a regional extent (Publication III), an initial spatial autocorrelation was observed up to 3,000 m, which is much greater than the median distance between the used soil profiles (535 m). Considering the study of McBratney and Pringle (1999), who stated that the spatial autocorrelations of numerous soil properties are smaller than 500 m (often < 100 m), the distance between the sampling points might still be too large, or the point density too low, to capture the full variability of soils, especially the chemical properties. In addition to general point density, even and full coverage of the variable space is also an important criterion for a successful modelling approach.

SxD- Solid rock, dolomite, poor in clay minerals

Occurrence of substrate type

Area	748.36 km ²
Percentage of total forest area	15.4 %

Physical soil properties- mean values according to field description (129)

Depth [cm]	Coarse fraction [%]	PAWC [l/m ²]
0-15	40 ± 30	40 ± 98
15-30	65 ± 30	
30-60	75 ± 20	
60-100	85 ± 20	

Carbon, nitrogen and nutrient stocks (2)

C _{tot} t/ha	N _{tot} t/ha	Ca kg/ha	Mg kg/ha	K kg/ha	P kg/ha
126.95	5.94	7316.5	1672.5	40.5	415

Mean stock values 0-80 cm of mineral soil and humus layers (OF,OH) given in short term availability. For phosphorous long-term availability is given.

Soil chemical analysis for depth intervals (46)

Depth [cm]	CEC [mmol/kg]	Base Saturation [%]	(Mg+Ca)/CEC	N _{tot} [%]	TOC [%]	C/N	pHCaCl ₂
0-5	692.7	99.65	0.99	0.76	14.29	18.8	6.45
5-10	690.73	99.65	0.99	0.75	14.06	18.75	6.45
10-20	531.35	99.93	1	0.53	9.07	17.11	6.85
20-40	359.70	99.98	1	0.29	5.26	18.14	7.05
40-80	293.57	99.98	1	0.23	4.45	19.35	7.17

Profile's depth variation of the following median chemical properties, bounded by 25th and 75th percentiles: cation exchange capacity (CEC, mmol/kg), nitrogen (N, %), total organic carbon (TOC, %), pH and base saturation (BS, %). Dark blue line represents median, blue area represents values within the second and third percentile.

Biomass use

Effects of whole-tree harvesting

Strong negative effects

Compaction risk

Effects of transit from heavy-duty machinery

Occasionally critical

Figure 10: Characterisation of forest soil properties based on a subsolum geological substrate unit.

The use of vegetation relevées and the response variables generated therefrom, such as Ellenberg's ecological indicator values (Ellenberg et al., 2001), can be discussed in the context of differences between the observation and modelling scales. The size of the vegetation relevées used is 400 m² (20 x 20 m) and the calculated mean soil reaction value is an integral of all occurring vascular plant species at that plot. In contrast, the modelling scale has a spatial resolution of 5 m. This aspect might often be overlooked and no information on this issue was found in the literature on the regionalisation of information from vegetation relevées (Reger et al., 2011; Häring et al., 2014). Regardless of the capacity of high resolution DTM derivatives to provide a detailed breakdown of the response variable information and its influence on modelling results, this limitation should be kept in mind when interpreting the regionalised information. On the other hand, using the integral of the spatial and temporal variability of sites is likely to improve the predictive power of the models, as shown in Publication III. Regarding the scale of the DTM derivatives used, the approach of Behrens et al. (2018) with multiple-scaled predictor variables seems to be promising for further improvements.

The observed potential of very detailed information on geological substrate information for digital soil mapping in mountain areas laid the foundation for Publication IV. This research topic, at the interface between the disciplines of geology and soil science, addresses the quantitative description of parent material as an important predictor in forest site characterisation and consequently also a forest ecosystem that is influenced by climate change (Fig. 2). A result of this description is given in Figure 10 for a subsolum geological substrate (SSGS) classified as SxD- (lithogenetic entity: 'Sx' = solid bedrock, undifferentiated; main geochemical entity: 'D' = Dolomite; impurity: '-': pure). The compiled dataset of soil analysis and recordings is used to characterise the physical and geochemical soil properties of the classification units. This includes the intensity parameters (e.g. pH value, base saturation), capacity parameters (e.g. cation exchange capacity (CEC), element stocks, PAWC), and ecologically meaningful ratios (e.g. C/N). For example, the proportion of Ca and Mg in the CEC ((Mg+Ca)/CEC, Fig. 10) was used to identify SSGS units with a high sensitivity to biomass removal and is important for the nutritional sustainability of forest management (Katzensteiner et al., 2016). This ratio comes into play if > 0.98 at SSGS units with high base saturation (> 70%) and low CEC (< 200 mmol*kg⁻¹). All physical and geochemical information results in practical recommendations for forest management in terms of sustainable biomass use and the compaction risks of the soil. As commonly implemented, these recommendations follow a traffic light system, from green with minor negative effects, to red with strong negative effects (Fig. 10). Another comparable practical application of the pedological interpretation of geological maps, albeit only for calcareous material, for forest site classification is given by Kolb and Göttlein (2019).

Even though the presented examples focus exclusively on the parent material for soil formation, other soil forming factors (Jenny, 1941) operate simultaneously, albeit not always in the same direction of soil formation. Since mountain areas, such as the Alps, often show a very high variety of geological substrates as a result of different sedimentation environments, processes of orogenesis, and quaternary landscape evolution, the diversity of soil formation pathways is high. Moreover, some of the soil forming factors, in particular human activity and time, can hardly be assessed at a regional scale. Nevertheless, attempts to assess these factors are promising as regards stimulating insight into soil formation and improved characterisation of current soil properties. Taking these constraints into account, the underlying dataset currently

covers 59 different SSGS classification units, representing approximately 95% of the forested area of Tyrol. The aggregated characterisation of forest soil properties of the SSGS units, as shown in Figure 10, is available in the Tyrolean Spatial Information System (TIRIS Maps).

The newly developed subsolum geological substrate information can stimulate further developments in digital soil mapping, especially in mountain environments. In addition, the characterisation of physical and geochemical soil properties results in practical recommendations for forest management in terms of sustainable biomass use and the risk of soil compaction.

4. Conclusion

Finding answers to urgent questions related to the impacts of and possible adaptation to climate change is one of the current challenges of forest site classification. This thesis started with a comprehensive overview of the concept, aims, and evolution of forest site classification in order to identify the current topics and developments. In this framework, the overall aim of developing, implementing, and evaluating spatial modelling methods for forest site classification in mountain areas was presented.

The relation to climate change effects and response strategies and the consideration of scale are the central themes and connecting links between the individual publications. The importance of climate change and its influences on forest ecosystems are discussed in myriads of publications and is not in doubt. At the same time, scale as well is an important methodological issue in forest ecology and site classification. Many patterns emerge only at a certain scale and are ascribed to noise or constants, or are not even recognised at other scales (Chave, 2013). The most prominent aspect of scale in modelling is the effect of resolution (the modelling scale), but the effect of extent with respect to the size of the study area might also play an important role.

The individual publications address different levels of spatial scale, defined by observation scale, modelling scale, which is defined by micro-, meso- and macro-scale, and modelling extent, which is defined by microsite, stand, hillslope, landscape, and regional levels. The applied classifications of the scales are not set in stone, rather they will change with ongoing technological development (e.g. the availability of high-resolution digital terrain models or remote sensing data) and a shift towards high-resolution modelling scale for all extents is likely. However, an increase in the resolution of the modelling scale does not automatically result in higher model accuracy and performance. Nevertheless, finer grained information may identify correlations that smooth out at a coarse granularity. In any case, the spatial extent and the modelling scale should fit the sampling point density, the spatial autocorrelation of the response variable, the spatial resolution of the predictor variables, and the underlying scale of the processes.

As a further development trajectory, the dynamic modelling of the site features that determine the characteristics of forest sites and species behaviour is a promising approach to forest site classification. At the current stage, dynamic site classification systems provide the starting and ending conditions of forest sites in time slices, but the successional pathways are rather unknown. The incorporation of climate-sensitive forest dynamic models for specific

forest site units is a promising approach to support decision-making in forest management. This leads back to the different aims and purposes of forest site classification, which have in common that they support the sustainable management of forest ecosystems.

Independent of the modelling approach and objective, holistic and spatially explicit models of forest ecosystems frequently require forest site information, especially on soil properties. In this work, the thesis on spatial modelling methods for forest site classification in mountain areas attempts to close the gap between sophisticated statistical methods and practical applications.

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Hinweis zur Einreichung für den Kubienapreis

Bis 31. August können Arbeiten für den Kubienapreis eingereicht werden.

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